

THE SPECIFICITY OF PROPER NAMES

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the ability of proper name to fulfill the identification function, to reflect the national and cultural features of society and serve as the carrier of additional linguistic and cultural information, especially in literary texts. The specificity of anthroponyms lies in their combination of identifying functions with high linguistic and cultural potential.

In order to clarify whether proper name has connotation it is vital to analyze what the specificity of proper name is. According to Superanskaya, it is necessary to examine a number of general linguistic categories, demonstrating their specificity in onomastics to clarify issues related to the semantics of proper names. These are: significance, importance, value, information, meaning, and function.

The significance of proper names is the presence of specific meanings in them. Just as common nouns, adjectives, adverbs, and verbs differ fundamentally on the one hand, and pronouns or numerals on the other, so too do proper nouns, which are notional rather than functional words, differ in their nature.

The specificity of anthroponyms consists of the following features: 1)Identifying function, 2)National and Cultural Determination, 3)Social informativeness, 3)Historical variability, 4)Semantic significance, 5)Expressive and stylistic function in fiction, 6)Variability of forms.

Anthroponyms serve to distinguish and identify a specific person among others.

Names reflect the cultural, historical, religious, and ethnic characteristics of a people. For example, the names "Otabek", "Charos", and "Ulugbek" are characteristic of Uzbek culture.

Anthroponyms can indicate a person's origin, social status, and membership in a particular family or clan.

The system of personal names changes over time under the influence of historical events, religion, fashion, and intercultural contacts.

Many anthroponyms have a specific meaning. For example, the name "Victor" means "winner", and the name "Timur" means "iron".

In literature, character names help reveal the character, create certain associations, and convey the author's intent. For example, in Charles Dickens, the names of some of the characters have a strong characterizing function.

A single name can have various formal and informal forms: Evgeniy- Jenya-Jenechka, Anastasiya- Nastya- Nastenka.

The value of the proper names is revealed only when we conduct a more detailed analysis. "Since this concept is a product of the system and does not exist outside of it, the value of individual names can only be discussed in cases where the entire system is considered. This applies primarily to the synchronic description of names existing in limited territories, as well as to closed communities, namely, to regional onomastic studies"¹

The most important specificity of proper names is information. Superenskaya believes that the information of proper names is not revealed to every person. She considers that three types of name information are distinguished: speech, linguistic and encyclopedic. Speech information connects the name with object and reveals the speaker's attitude to the object. It is the most widespread and general information of name. Encyclopedic information – is a complex of knowledge about an object, accessible to each member of the language community, which uses this name. The linguistic information of a name is the most constant and unchanging part of its information. It consists of the nature and composition of the name's components.

Speaking about meaning, it is vital to differentiate concept and meaning. "Not every word meaning is a concept, since words, in addition to expressing conceptual content, perform a number of other functions (expressive, stylistic, and so on). If...we consider concepts to be only those thoughts that have the form of an actual or possible answer to the question "What is this?" or "What is it?", then we must recognize that not every use of a word is an expression of a concept, although every use of a word contains a general meaning"².

Some linguists wrote that the meaning of proper name, from a logical point of view, the meaning of a proper name is limited to the fact that it serves merely as a means of identifying individual objects, things, and persons. Its interpretation is possible only within a poetic or expressive-emotional framework, because it is always unique and entirely specific, whereas a common noun dialectically combines the concrete designation of an object with its general concept.

Studying proper names in text reveals the difference in the semantics of a single lexical unit being studied and the same unit immersed in the text. Studying proper names within the framework of the name-in-text idea allowed some linguists to identify certain possibilities revealed by proper names. Namely: proper name indicates the social context of a new era, when the requirements for nomination change; proper name in one system shows a connection with a common name in another system; closely analyzing a familiar proper name turns out to be a memory of the past preserved in the hidden linguistic memory of a particular ethnic group; proper names of one literary work provide the reader with keys to characters in other texts;

¹ Суперанская А. В. Общая теория имени собственного. -М: Наука, 2012.

² Ахманов А.С. Логические формы и их выражение в языке. «Мышление и язык». -М., 1957.

proper names of characters in a text can echo each other , creating extra meaning for a particular character.

The list of used literature:

1. Суперанская А. В. Общая теория имени собственного. -М: Наука, 2012.
2. Ахманов А.С. Логические формы и их выражение в языке. «Мышление и язык». – М., 1957.
3. Винокур Г.О. О некоторых явлениях словообразования в русской
4. технической терминологии. «Труды МИФЛИ», – 1939, т.5.
5. Топоров В.Н. Из области теоретической топониматики. -М., 1962
6. Флоренский П. А. Малое собрание сочинений. Вып. I: Имена. – Кострома,
7. –1993.
8. Хазагеров Т. Г. Стилистические функции антономасии и трудности ее
9. выявления в рассказах А. П. Чехова // Языковое мастерство А. П. Чехова. –
10. Ростов-на-Дону, 1988.
11. Хриненко Ю.Н. К вопросу о значении имени собственного: (На материале
12. англ. личных имен) // Семантические аспекты языка. – Л., 1981.
13. Щаренская Н.М. Концепт «футляр» // Концептосфера А.П.Чехова. Сборник
14. статей. Изд. Южного Федерального университета. Ростов-на-Дону, 2009. Стр.
15. 145-172.

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